

Studies on Hydrated Stannic Oxide as Anion Exchanger : Part I. Synthesis, Properties and Anion-Exchange Behaviour of Hydrated Stannic Oxide

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A new method has been proposed for the preparation of hydrated stannic oxide suitable for use as an anion exchanger. It is prepared from sodium stannate via ammonium stannate decomposition and has been compared with hydrated stannic oxide prepared from three other different methods. Preparative procedure, chemical stability, pH titration, heat treatment and ion-exchange capacity of these materials are reported and discussed.

HYDRATED stannic oxide is now known as a cation exchanger¹⁻³ as well as an anion exchanger⁴. In our laboratory hydrated stannic oxide⁵ prepared from decomposition of ammonium stannate has been proved very satisfactory for the separation of various anionic species by paper chromatography.

This paper reports systematic and comparative studies on chemical stability, pH titration curves, thermogravimetric analysis, infra-red spectra and ion-exchange capacity of hydrated stannic oxide prepared by four different methods. Such studies will be helpful for the separation of various anionic species by column chromatography.

Experimental

Reagents : Granulated tin was of reagent grade quality (PFIZER). Sodium stannate was of reagent grade quality (U. S. S. R.). All other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

Apparatus : pH measurements were made with an ELICO MODEL LI-10 pH meter. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using a spectromom 202 instrument (Mom, Budapest, Hungary). An Owa Labor Type 707.04 analytical balance was used.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis : The condition of synthesis of hydrated stannic oxide by four different methods are summarised in Table 1. The products were filtered off and washed with distilled water till the pH of the filtrate was 3.0-3.5 (in the case of batch 1) and 7.5 to 8.0 (in the case of batch 2, 3 and 4). The exchangers were dried at $(60 \pm 5)^\circ$.

Composition : Tin was determined iodimetrically⁶ as well as gravimetrically as SnO_2 . About 1 g of the exchanger was weighed accurately in a silica crucible. It was ignited at 800° in a muffle furnace

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF EXCHANGERS

Batch No.	Reagents used	Mixing ratio	Temp. and time	Drying temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Appearance in OH form	pH of mother liquor after synthesis	Chemical Composition $\text{SnO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$
1.	Metallic tin + Conc. HNO_3	3 : 10 Wt/Vol.	Room temp. overnight	60 ± 5	White crystalline	HNO_3 medium	1 : 1.64
2.	$\text{Na}_2\text{SnO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1(M) + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 1(M)	1 : 1 Vol/Vol.	Room temp. overnight	60 ± 5	White crystalline	8.0	1 : 2.12
3.	$\text{Na}_2\text{SnO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.5(M) + HCl , 2(M)	1 : 1 Vol/Vol.	Room temp. overnight	60 ± 5	White crystalline	9.0	1 : 1.49
4.	$\text{Na}_2\text{SnO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.5(M) + HCl , 2(M)	1 : 1 Vol/Vol.	Reflux 4 hrs.	60 ± 5	White crystalline	8.9	1 : 1.57

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and weighed. The difference in weight was the amount of water lost, and the weight of the residue was the amount of anhydrous tin(IV) dioxide. From this result the water of crystallisation was calculated by the method of Alberti et al⁷. Compositions of hydrated tin(IV) dioxide are given in the Table 1.

Chemical Stability : Detailed studies on the solubility of the exchangers were carried out by the following procedure : The exchanger (500 mg) was shaken with 50 ml of required solvent for 4 hrs at room temperature. Tin was determined from the filtrate iodimetrically⁶. The solubility was also determined by refluxing the exchanger with 50 ml of the solvent for 1 hr. The exchanger (batch 1 and 2) is fairly stable in water, 1 (M) hydrochloric acid, 1.5 (M) sulphuric acid, 0.5 (M) perchloric acid, 0.5 (M) sodium hydroxide and 0.1 (M) ammonium hydroxide. The exchanger is also fairly stable in mixed solvent systems (20% acetic acid+normal butanol+acetone=2 : 2 : 1 Vol/Vol, 2(M) hydrochloric acid+ethanol=2 : 3 Vol/Vol).

Heat Treatment : About one gram of hydrated stannic oxide was taken in a silica crucible and heated from 100° to 800° in steps of 100° in a muffle furnace for 1 hr. The colour of the samples (batch 2 and batch 3) remained unchanged. The solubility of the exchanger decreases with the increase of temperature to which the exchanger has been heated. It was observed that the mode of water removal by heating was quite different in the case of batch 2 from batch 1. There was no weight loss of batch 2 between 200° to 300°. Hence two water molecules present in the hydrated stannic oxide (batch 2) are not equivalent. Presumably one water molecule is present at the interstitial water molecule.

I. R. Spectra : In each case a broad peak was obtained for all the samples at 3100-3500 cm⁻¹ and another less broad peak at 1630 cm⁻¹ for weakly adsorbed water, Peak at 3400 cm⁻¹ is due to OH-stretching and peak at 1630 cm⁻¹ is due to H-O-H bending. Two peaks at 990 cm⁻¹ and 1250 cm⁻¹ which may be due to coordinated water molecule were observed in batch 2 and 3 only. These two peaks are not prominent in batch 4 and are absent in batch 1. The broad peak at 600 cm⁻¹ is due to Sn-O polymerization.

pH titration curves : For pH titration (batch 1 and 2) Topp and Pepper's⁸ method was employed.

The pH titration was performed with nitric acid, sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, acetic acid, oxalic acid and citric acid. As there is only one break in the titration curve, the exchangers should comprise monofunctional base. The titration curves with Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ lie closer to each other at high pH values, but at lower pH the curve for Cl⁻ lies between those for NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ for

batch 1 and the curve for NO₃⁻ lies between those for Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ for batch 2.

On titration with acid alone there is more rapid decrease in pH than in presence of the salt (e.g., NaNO₃). The addition of sodium nitrate releases some OH⁻ from the exchanger and this increases the pH.

Column Elution of Hydroxyl Ion : Hydrated stannic oxide is an anion exchanger. The anion exchange capacity, which is generally taken as the measure of the OH⁻ ion liberated by a neutral salt such as sodium chloride, is found to depend upon the concentration and volume of the eluent for column operation. A column (1.1 cm i.d.) was prepared by one gram of the exchanger (Batch 2) and washed with double distilled water to remove any free alkali present. The OH⁻ ion liberated by sodium chloride was estimated volumetrically using methyl orange indicator. The results with 1(M) and 2(M) sodium chloride +HCl solution are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Elution curve of hydroxyl ion of hydrated stannic oxide (Batch No. 2). Continuous line, eluent 2M NaCl dotted line, eluent 1M NaCl.

The exchange proceeds rapidly at first but elution continues for a long time. The reaction can be postulated as

where MOH represent the hydroxyl form of the exchanger.

Ion-exchange Capacity : The effect of concentration of the neutral salt sodium chloride and time of equilibrium on the exchange capacity of hydrated

stannic oxide (batch 1 and 2) (OH^- form) were studied by batch operation⁹. A constant exchange capacity was obtained for sodium chloride solution of concentration greater than 1.0(M) (batch 2) and 1.5(M) (batch 1). It required 4 hrs (batch 2) and 3 hrs (batch 1) for complete equilibrium to be attained.

The total ion-exchange capacity of hydrated stannic oxide for chloride ion was determined by batch operation¹⁰. The ion-exchange capacity of hydrated stannic oxide for chloride ion decreases with the temperature to which the exchanger has been heated. The retaining of ion exchange capacity of batch 2,3 and 4 is higher upto 700° when compared to batch 1.

Hydrated stannic oxide behave both as cation exchanger as well as anion exchanger. The exchange capacity for both univalent cation and anion of batch 1 and 2 was determined at different pH. The plot of ion-exchange capacity against pH (Fig. 2) shows that anion exchange capacity decreases with increase of pH whereas cation exchange capacity increases with increase of pH. The point of intersection (isoelectric point) of the two curves for batch 1 is at pH 4.80 and that for batch 2 is at pH 6.35. From the difference of isoelectric point it is assumed that the basicity of batch 2 is greater than that of batch 1.

Fig. 2. Exchange capacity of hydrated stannic oxide as a function of pH. \circ Batch 1; \triangle Batch 2.

The amount of dichromate ion adsorbed by the exchangers (batch 1 and 2) was determined at different pH. It was observed that the adsorption of dichromate ion decreases with increase of pH. The amount of dichromate adsorbed by batch 2 (4.5 mg) at pH 5.9 is greater than that for batch 1 (1.4 mg). This is in agreement with the fact that the isoelectric point of batch 2 is higher than that for batch 1.

When batch 2 is heated to 300° its chemical stability is increased and its ion-exchange capacity still remained to be 1.008 mequiv/g. So we recommend batch 2 after heating at 300° for ion-exchange separation. It will be suitable for exchange reaction at high temperature.

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